

Transactional Academic Leadership Effect on Employee's Engagement: the Mediating Impact of Extrinsic Motivation

Kebede Asefa¹, Dr. Shashi Kant²

¹Research Scholar, College of Business and Economics, Department of Management, Bule Hora University, Ethiopia.

²Assistant Professor, College of Business and Economics, Department of Management, Bule Hora University, Ethiopia. [orcid-id-0000-0003-4722-5736](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4722-5736).

Abstract – Employee's engagement has been at the core of consideration for top management and scholars who stated that employee's engagement can be a key driver of an organization's business success. Many scholars have found in recent researches that a transactional academic leadership approach has a beneficial connection with employees engagement. Therefore, this research oriented to investigate the connection of transactional academic leadership on employees engagement through the mediating role of figurehead extrinsic enthusiasm. Researchers examine the information from a sample of 338 elevated education employees working in the elevated academic institutes in Ethiopia by means of structural equation modeling (SEM) and confirmatory factor investigation (CFA) to examine the framed hypothesis. Afterward, the bootstrapping investigation was employed to verify the mediation examine in present research. The investigation manifested that transactional academic leadership approach had considered proficient impact on employee's engagement for the mediating role of extrinsic enthusiasm. The impact of transactional academic leadership on employee's engagement was found to be totally mediated by figurehead extrinsic enthusiasm. Hypothetically, present experiential investigation contributed to the novel knowledge on the exclusive mediating impacts of figurehead extrinsic motivation on the connections among

transactional academic leadership and employee's engagement in the Ethiopia. Practically, present research has administrative connotation in the field of governmental administration and leadership.

Keywords: Employees Engagement, Extrinsic Enthusiasm, Transactional Academic Leadership, Transactional Leadership.

1. INTRODUCTION

Global level change to educating employees about implementation of change, management of change and converting challenge to opportunity in time of change is the responsibility of transactional academic leadership. By these elevated academic institutes are the harbinger for educating next generation and managing the rising poverty and social problems. Transformations concerning leadership in education also attractively involve educators and facilitate them to be proficient to impart their learners a wealthy and friendly learning ecosystem (Al-Husseini et al., 2021). A transactional university leader ensures learners focus on their studies by being thoughtful of personality, being charismatic in influencing and inspiring. In its place of by means of fixed problem-solving techniques, they involve learners and educators to come up with solutions to problems as they arise (Bak et al., 2022). The benefits of transactional academic leadership methods of educators encompasses in empowering and rising learner enthusiasm, augment learning and engagement of learners, experiencing success,

civilizing learners' presentation and attainment, rising superiority of connections in physical learning (Al-Matroushi & Al-Kiyumi, 2022).

Research outcomes concluded that transformative leadership is associated with employees engagement (Meng et al., 2022). Transactional leaders inspire their employees to achieve elevated success by establishing a good-looking and thrilling apparition, setting challenging goals, being positive and optimistic and emphasizing group job (Anggiani, 2022). On the one hand, leadership is entrusted with articulating apparition, which has an impact on employees engagement in its own right. Employees are more inspired to do their job when they believe in a elevated purpose and are aligned with the company's mission (Beatrice, 2022). On the other hand, having a strong transactional academic leadership climate is also associated with better academic health in eight countries. Finally, the augmentation impact was consider proficient in six countries and we also found, as expected, that a elevated power distance strengthens the health promoting impacts of transactional academic leadership (Oloan, 2022). Transactional academic leadership received considers proficient attention in the literature sector and concluded that transactional academic leadership and employee's engagement are positively related. The systematic research investigating the connection ship among transactional academic leadership and employee's engagement but yielding mixed outcomes inspired the present research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Employees engagement is a phenomenon that has garnered considers proficient attention because of the many desired positive consequences of employee's engagement that benefit the firms that employ workers (HIM, 2021). In today's aggressive business world, employee's engagement has become an indispensable proficient element for organizational success and excellence. Leadership is considered to be the most proficient and critical

aspect for organization's progression. Transactional leaders nurture a better participation in the employment of subordinates resulting in elevated competence and sense of fulfillment, hence elevating on the whole employee's engagement level in organization. Both leadership and employees engagement are one of the most researched subjects in HRM; however, concerning transactional academic leadership to employees engagement has not been comprehensively investigated (Lai, 2020). Employees engagement is the "extraction of association members' personality with their assigned task; in engagement, employees occupy and express themselves bodily, cognitively, and psychologically for the duration of responsibility presentation" (Siangchokyoo et al., 2020). Bakker & Albrecht (2018) showed that manager should address the importance and benefit of employees engagement because it will augment employees presentation, augment task intelligence of fulfillment, and guide the association to attain goals. The stage to which a staff members' cognitive, expressive, and behavioral condition is sloping in the direction of proficient outcomes is referred to as employee's engagement. Charoensukmongkol & Puyod (2021) assume the subsequent description for employee's engagement: employees engagement is the quantity to which a staff member is psychologically, cognitively, and behaviorally associated to the job-oriented outcomes of the company.

Equation of structural modeling manifested that, the connection ships among transactional academic leadership and extrinsic motivation are mediated by the extrinsic motivation (Fauzan et al., 2021). Transactional leaders inspire and encourage their job force devoid of attitude development. Transactional leader's have faith on skilled employees to take power in excess of taking decisions. It's a supervision practice that's intended to pass on employee's additional opportunity to be artistic, look to the prospect and investigate novel solutions to getting on troubles (Krishna et al., 2022). From side to side the potency of Transactional

leader's spirit and qualities, transactional leaders are proficient to inspire supporters to modify prospect, perceptions, and enthusiasms to job towards universal goals (Maryani & Finthariasari, 2021). Extrinsic motivation refers to the figurehead ability to inspire confidence, extrinsic motivation and a sense of purpose in his supporters. The transactional leader must articulate a clear apparition for the future, communicate expectations of the group and demonstrate a commitment to the goals that have been laid out (Wibowo & Sumiati, 2022). Transactional academic leadership influences the primary attitudes and hypothesis of an organization's members, nurturing a universal state of mind to achieve the organizational goals. This leadership approach frequently generates elevated success than transactional leadership (Chua & Ayoko, 2021).

Extrinsic motivation refers to a staff members' instinctive drive to do well and obtain possession of their job because leaders take pleasure in their task. Leaders also get pleasure from the self-importance and common sense of fulfillment that they experience at a task (Engidaw, 2021). By the side of its nucleus, nurturing extrinsic motivation is about serving employees turn out to be additional creative, engaged and more contented in their job (Yousaf et al., 2022). The investigation accomplished that there is a optimistic connection ship among extrinsic motivation and employees engagement, and academic leadership and employees engagement. Additionally, it is also manifested together extrinsic and academic transactional leadership has a well-built optimistic impact on employees engagement (Fishbach & Woolley, 2022). Engagement is wisdom of intention, commitment, and obligation to an organization, whereas extrinsic motivation is the willpower and drives to perform on those thoughts. Employees engagement serves as a sub-structure for employees to do their most excellent job, while extrinsic motivation is the stimulation or power required to really do it (Chen et al., 2021). The outcomes showed that teacher's extrinsic motivation has optimistic connection with

staff members' task success and extrinsic motivation has impact on staff members' task performance. Investigations also demonstrate that females are extra extrinsic ally enthused as compared to males (Novitasari et al., 2021).

Fig -1: Researchers Schematic Model (2022)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

Present investigation applies the research approach in form of quantitative approach engages measuring information on variables (transactional leadership, teachers extrinsic motivation and employee engagement), by means of quantitative scales and quantitative data investigation. Proceeding to field studies, researchers execute an exploratory factor exploration (EFA) based on the hundred responses from the pilot study to authenticate the magnitude of the proxies and confirm an internal reliability for every variable used in the research.

3.1 Sampling and information collection

The data collection instrument was provided with directions to comprehensive all the points appropriately. Provocation letters were also provided after the approval of competent authority, and it serve the privacy of the respondents. The statistics of data collection instrument received back by the respondents were 352 that represented a return rate of 82%. Incomplete survey responses were 9. Hence, 341 size of sample were considered for auxiliary investigation by means of AMOS 26 of IBM SPSS.

3.2 Variable Dimensions

Researchers employ a 5-point likert scale to gauge the intensity of staff members' perception towards the itemized testimonial in the data collection instrument connecting transactional leadership, teacher's extrinsic motivation and employees engagement to congregate the obligation for information assumption by means of parametric investigation.

4. INVESTIGATION AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Evaluation of for information set normality

For research normality evaluation, researchers experiential the skewness measurement that demonstrated the ordinary distribution for each variable item such as transactional academic leadership (TEL), extrinsic Motivation (IM), and employees engagement (SME). Skewness measurement values lies under the range of -1.4 and 1.5 that demonstrated that data was normally distributed and suitable for further analysis.

4.2 Investigation of factors of Confirmation

Researchers by the implication of CFA, confirmatory factor investigation investigated the model fitness

by use of indices. Values of indices manifested the covariance amongst items of model of measurement within transactional academic leadership, teacher's extrinsic motivation and employee's engagement. Formerly the description of CFA was accomplished and each and every one values convene the necessary thresholds for reliability and validity, researchers found that the model of measurement intended for each, and every one dormant (latent) variables concerned in the measurement model have been authenticated (Awang, 2015). Subsequently, researchers bring together variables into the model of structural equation to perform structural equation modelling (SEM). Researchers put together in sequence of right to extreme left, commencement through the exogenous variables pursue by in the middle of mediator variables, and far right locate the endogenous variable (Awang, 2015).

Followed by substrate on the course of the assumption, in figure 2 by using the single headed arrow researchers connects the exogenous variable to its particular endogenous variable. Researchers had placed the AMOS 26 based structural model as concluded in figure 2 for computation of weights for standardized and un-standardized regression model. Model fitness tested with help of fit indices manifested the model is statistically fitted under desired parameters.

Fig -2: SEM MODEL

Table -1: Indices Results Based On Parameters

Indices	Observed Value	Result
Bollen's incremental fit index (IFI)	0.901	<i>Under Acceptance Level</i>
Chi-Square Fit Statistics/Degree Of Freedom (CMIN/DF)	2.23	<i>Under Acceptance Level</i>
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.903	<i>Under Acceptance Level</i>
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) (Close Fit* Hypothesis- parsimony-adjusted index)	0.061	<i>Probability of receiving a sample was 0.061 from 0.080.</i>

Factor loading of whole residual items, as revealed in Figure 2, had the values more than the requisite value of 0.6. Therefore, researchers may possibly presume that the measurement model unidimensionality had been achieved. Consequently, researcher's content through the explored index fitness and the confirmatory factor investigation (CFA) concluded that *modus operandi* was accomplished at this phase previous to structural modeling preceding. Following table shows the achieved Composite reliability (CR) requirements and average variance extracted (AVE) for factoring all items.

Table -2: Composite Reliability (CR) Requirements and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

S.No.	Items	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted
1.	Transactional Academic Leadership	0.92	0.76
2.	Teachers Extrinsic Motivation	0.94	0.80
3.	Employees Engagement	0.88	0.72

4.3 Testing of Hypothesis: analyzing mediating function of extrinsic motivation on the effect of transactional academic leadership on employees engagement

In present study, researchers hypothesize that as a variable extrinsic motivation mediates the impact

from an exogenous variable of transactional academic leadership to its endogenous variable of employees engagement. The conjecture is that if the direct impact of transactional academic leadership to employees engagement does not exist in the structural model, but the impact exists indirectly through another variable of extrinsic motivation; then in this research extrinsic motivation is a mediating variable.

Fig. 2 manifested the position of extrinsic motivation among transactional academic leadership and employees engagement.

The result showed that the probability of getting a critical ratio of 12.379 in absolute value was less than 0.001. In other words, the regression weight for transactional academic leadership when concluded extrinsic motivation consider proficiently differed from zero at 0.001 levels.

Besides, the probability of obtaining a critical ratio of 1.851 in absolute value was 0.064. In other words, the regression weight for transactional academic leadership when employees engagement did not consider proficiently differ from zero at 0.05 levels (two-tails).

The probability of obtaining a critical ratio of 2.363 in absolute value was 0.018. In other words, the regression weight for extrinsic motivation when employees engagement significantly differed from zero at 0.001 levels (two-tails). Based on the investigation, the above research hypothesis was facilitated.

This research concludes that construct has considered proficiently mediated the connection ship among transactional academic leadership and employee's engagement. As illustrated before, the type of mediation is called a "complete mediation" since the direct impact of the transactional academic leadership on employees engagement was no longer consider proficient after construct entered the model. The beta coefficient for transactional academic leadership was reduced from 0.575 to 0.241. Hence, in this research,

transactional academic leadership had considered proficient indirect impact on employees engagement through the mediator proficient, namely construct.

4.4 Mediation of Teacher’s Extrinsic Motivation

The method for examining extrinsic motivation mediator role:

- 1) The indirect impact = $0.93 \times 0.43 = 0.40$;
- 2) The direct impact = -0.33 ;
- 3) Both indirect paths are considered proficient;
- 4) Since indirect impact > direct impact, the mediation occurs;
- 5) Type of mediation is complete mediation since the direct impact is not considered proficient after mediator enters the model.

In examining the hypothesis for the mediation impact of teacher’s extrinsic motivation in linking transactional academic leadership with employee’s engagement, the hypothesis was supported. Consequently, this research concluded that TIM has considered proficiently mediated the connection ship among transactional academic leadership and employee’s engagement. Hence, these investigations have answered the research question: Does a figurehead TIM mediate the impact of transactional leadership on employee’s engagement?

To discover the type of mediation, these investigating also provided a calculation for the impact size of mediation. In calculating the impact size of a mediator in the mediating impact, it was found that the impact size of teacher’s extrinsic motivation on employee’s engagement was in the small range.

In this research, the impact size is the amounts of variance explained in the mediation model contribute by every single path. Again, these investigating closed the gaps found in the previous researches by linking teacher’s extrinsic motivation

as a mediator in the connection ship among transactional academic leadership and employee’s engagement. This research has not only concluded the type of mediation, but also the impact size of teacher’s extrinsic motivation (TIM) on employee’s engagement (SME).

Proficient 1. Examining TEM as a mediator in the connection ship among TEL and SME			
Connection ship	Standardized (β)	P-Value	Result
TEL → TIM (a)	0.94	***	Consider proficient
TIM → SME (b)	0.43	0.18	Consider proficient
TEL → SME (c)	0.332	0.064	Not Consider proficient
a*b		0.40	
a*b > c		Mediation occurs	

(Source: AMOS 26 OUTPUTS, 2022)

Proficient 2. Bootstrapping Result		
Indirect Impact P- Value	Direct Impact P-Value	
Bootstrapping P-Value	0.000	0.064
Result	Consider proficient	Not Consider proficient
Type of Mediation	Complete Mediation	

(Source: AMOS 26 OUTPUTS, 2022)

5. CONCLUSIONS

Present research focused the method fundamental on the impacts of transactional academic leadership on staff engagement from the perspective of mediating part of teacher extrinsic motivation. The investigation of present research specify that teacher extrinsic motivation adds to the intensification of the correlation among transactional academic leadership and employees engagement and there was collision function of the mediators when inter the model and the size of this impact was in small range. Present research assists Ghadi, et al. (2013) suggestions that supplementary mediators may affect the relation flanked by transactional academic leadership and employees engagement which need to examine. In this regard, present research frame job can be comprehensive to supplementary studies in a different context other than education sector. At the same time as the majority engagement studies have greatly paying attention on linking employees engagement to organizational job circumstances, this investigation provides empirical evidence represented that

employees engagement reflects a two-way connection ship.

The investigations of this research add to the academic writing by provided that imperative information on the subject of the correlation among leadership and educator extrinsic motivation and employees engagement, which have not been previously investigated in a single research. From a practitioner’s perspective, the investigations from this research put forward that for educators who show the transactional academic leadership behavior and extrinsic motivation are more suit proficient for engaging employees at job place. Exclusively, these implications concentrate on issues related to organization of presentation, teaching and expansion, task intend, employment and assortment. The potential drawbacks of present study merely can be comprehensive to a populace of employees working in Bule Hora University, Ethiopia, higher academic institute in Ethiopia due to diverse backgrounds in special context of studies.

Moreover, the investigating originates from existing investigation recommended that there is a need for potential examine based on the assessments of the explicit magnitudes of teachers extrinsic motivation affecting employee engagement necessitate supplementary investigation may be in the significance of extrinsic motivation behaviors that consider both the leader and employees, rather than the extrinsic motivation behaviors that describe the behaviors of only the leader.

6. FUTURE IMPLICATION

This study is significant for the government to revise his policy to give a solution for personal and organizational –related, legal/administration, economic, social/cultural and other factors that affect the perception of women entrepreneurs in entrepreneurial activities. It also enables them what types of policy need to be adopted to encourage the participation and achievement of potential and existing women entrepreneurs. Finally, the study helps other researchers to predict the factors

affecting the perception of women entrepreneurs in the same study area and provide the deep understanding of the critical factors that affect the perception of women entrepreneurs in general.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Kebede Asefa and Dr. Shashi Kant contributed equally to this manuscript. It is the Kebede Asefa research work during his PhD paper completion that was assisted by the Dr. Shashi Kant. The authors would like to thank all Bule Hora University, Ethiopia employees who assisted them to complete this research.

8. COMPLIANCE WITH ETHICAL STANDARDS

The present research work closely followed all ethical standards established by the Institutional Review Board at the author’s university “Bule Hora University”, Oromia, Ethiopia and the participating college. The study was reviewed by the “Department Graduate Committee” (DGC) for the college of Business and Economics, Bule Hora University, Ethiopia, headed by the college Dean. Prior consent for information was obtained from the study participants and informed them in advanced that the information was collected only for academic research purpose. It is confirmation that the guidelines outlined in the Declaration of University were followed.

9. FUNDING

The study was self-financed by the researchers. No external funding assistance was availed by the authors.

10. DISCLOSURE

The authors declare no conflicts of interest in this research work.

REFERENCES

- [1] Al-Husseini, S., El Beltagi, I., & Moizer, J. (2021). Transactional academic leadership and innovation: the mediating role of knowledge sharing amongst elevated education faculty. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 24(5), 670–693.
- [2] Al-Matroushi, S., & Al-Kiyumi, M. (2022). Impact of Transformative Leadership Practices of Academic Supervisors on the Sustain proficient Professional Development of Mathematics Educators. *Journal of Academic and Social Research*, 12(1), 261–261.
- [3] Anggiani, S. (2022). Influence of Transactional academic leadership on Task Performance: Employees Job Engagement as Examine Mediation. *Indonesian Management and Accounting Research*, 20(1), 33–44.
- [4] Bak, H., Jin, M. H., & McDonald III, B. D. (2022). Unpacking the Transactional Leadership–Innovative Job Behavior Connection ship: The Mediating Role of Psychological Capital. *Public Success& Management Review*, 45(1), 80–105.
- [5] Beatrice, S. (2022). Improving Employees Engagement through Leadership Approach. *Muma Business Review*, 5, 005–007.
- [6] Charoensukmongkol, P., & Puyod, J. V. (2021). Influence of transactional academic leadership on role ambiguity and job–life balance of Filipino University employees during COVID-19: does employees involvement matter? *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 1–20.
- [7] Chen, Y., Zhang, J., Liu, C. E., Liu, T., & He, W. (2021). Job-related identity discrepancy and employees innovation behavior: the role of extrinsic motivation and self-construal. *Chinese Management Studies*.
- [8] Chua, J., & Ayoko, O. B. (2021). Staff members' self-determined enthusiasm, transactional academic leadership and job engagement. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 27(3), 523–543.
- [9] Engidaw, A. E. (2021). The impact of extrinsic motivation on employees engagement in public sectors: in the case of North Wollo zone. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 10(1), 1–15.
- [10] Fauzan, S., Mariyah, S., & Setiaji, Y. T. (2021). The Influence of Transactional academic leadership in Moderating Task Sense of fulfillment and extrinsic motivation on Educators' Task Performance. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 173, 300–307.
- [11] Fishbach, A., & Woolley, K. (2022). The structure of extrinsic enthusiasm. *Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior*, 9.
- [12] HIM, L. (2021). TRANSACTIONAL EDUACTIONAL LEADERSHIP AND EMPLOYEES ENGAGEMENT AMONG FINANCE AND INSURANCE PROFESSIONALS IN MALAYSIA: ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AS A MEDIATOR.
- [13] Krishna, C., Upadhyay, R. K., Ansari, K. R., & Babu, V. (2022). Transactional academic leadership and employees retention: a moderated mediation model of extrinsic motivation and academic organizational facilitate. *International Journal of Learning and Intellectual Capital*, 19(2), 135–153.
- [14] Lai, F. Y., Tang, H. C., Lu, S. C., Lee, Y. C., & Lin, C. C. (2020). Transactional academic leadership and task performance: The mediating role of job engagement. *Sage Open*, 10(1), 2158244019899085.
- [15] Lauritzen, H. H., Grøn, C. H., & Kjeldsen, A. M. (2021). Leadership matters, but so do co-jobbers: A research of the relative importance of transactional academic leadership and team connections for employees outcomes and user sense of fulfillment. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 0734371X211011618.
- [16] Maryani, S., & Finthariasari, M. (2021). PENGARUH TRANSACTIONAL EDUACTIONAL LEADERSHIP TERHADAP EXTRINSIC MOTIVATIONPADA KARYAWAN BANK BRI CABANG CURUP. *JURNAL MANAJEMEN MODAL INSANI DAN BISNIS (JMMIB)*, 2(2), 122–128.
- [17] Meng, F., Xu, Y., Liu, Y., Zhang, G., Tong, Y., & Lin, R. (2022). Linkages among Transactional Leadership, Job Meaningfulness and Job Engagement: A Multilevel Cross-Sectional Research. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 15, 367.
- [18] Novitasari, D., Haque, M. G., Supriatna, H., Asbari, M., & Purwanto, A. (2021). Understanding the Links among Charismatic Leadership, Extrinsic motivation and Tacit Knowledge Sharing among MSME Staff members. *International Journal of Social and Management Studies*, 2(3), 1–13.
- [19] Oloan, D. (2022). The Connection ship among Transactional Leadership, Training, and And Employees Involvement as an Intervention on Employees Performance. *The Management Journal of Binaniaga*, 6(2), 151–164.
- [20] Siangchokyoo, N., Klinger, R. L., & Campion, E. D. (2020). Supporter transformation as the linchpin of transactional academic leadership theory: A systematic review and future research agenda. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 31(1), 101341.
- [21] Wibowo, A., & Sumiati, S. (2022). STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE LEARNING ORIENTATION THROUGH EXTRINSIC ENTHUSIASM, TRANSACTIONAL EDUACTIONAL LEADERSHIP AND GROWTH MINDSET. *International Journal of Business and Economy*, 4(1), 164–176.

- [22] Yousaf, S., Rasheed, M. I., Kaur, P., Islam, N., & Dhir, A. (2022). The dark side of plumbing in the job place: Investigating the role of extrinsic motivation and the use of enterprise social media (ESM) in a cross-cultural setting. *Journal of Business Research*, 143, 81–93.